

External debt burden and economic growth: evidence from Central Asia.

Mubinzhon Abduvaliev

Department of Economics. Faculty of International Economic Relations and Law
Tajik State University of Commerce, Dushambe, Tajikistan.
orcid.org/0000-0003-3576-5014

Ricardo Bustillo*

Email: ricardo.bustillo@ehu.es

Department of Public Policy and Economic History
University of Basque Country, UPV/EHU, Bilbao, Spain.
orcid.org/0000-0001-7246-8735

Abstract

The main goal of this paper is to analyze the effects of external debt accumulation on economic growth amongst Central Asian countries. We have applied a time series methodology utilizing annual data from 2000 to 2017 to show that external debt has had a negative and significant effect on economic growth in Central Asian countries. We found that debt overhang will cause a higher marginal tax rate on the future output of each country, thus leading to an investment slowdown and reducing output growth by limiting productivity expansion. Moreover, we can affirm that the negative effect of external debt is often associated with the poor level of institutions and governance of Central Asian countries.

Keywords: Central Asia; external debt burden; threshold level; economic growth; institutional quality.

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*Corresponding Author

1. Introduction

Developing countries have frequently suffered the need of external financial resources in order to correct their internal and external imbalances, as well as to promote economic growth and social development. Empirical literature usually insists on the negative effect of excessive external debt (Pattillo et al. 2002); however, external debt might have a positive effect if used effectively for the purpose of economic development and other national objectives. Macroeconomic stability and economic growth are enhanced when previously borrowed financial resources are reasonably utilized (Burnside and Dollar, 2000).

However, empirical evidence regarding the role of debt in the growth process among developing countries shows mixed results. Some researchers have tried to prove the positive effect of debt on economic growth empirically. Their view is based on the Keynesian and neoclassical theory of growth, according to which external debt contributes to higher economic growth rates, whenever a productive use of borrowed funds takes place. This approach has been supported by Warner (1992); Cline (1995); and Easterly (2003). Opposing this view, the Ricardian equivalence hypothesis stated “public debt had a neutral or irrelevant effect on economic growth” (Szabo, 2013: 251)

From a financial point of view, when external debt is optimally utilized and the marginal return of investment is greater than the cost of borrowing, the debt burden is not a serious concern. Supporting this argument, Abbas (2004) found a significant

positive growth payoff to debt even until debt/GDP ratio reaches 91%. He used panel data for 93 low-income and emerging countries over the 1975-2004 period. Additionally, Mahmoud (2015) examined the case of Mauritania over the period 1970-2011 to reveal that there was a positive relationship between GDP and external debt and a negative relationship between GDP and debt service.

However, some studies have found an ambiguous effect of debt on growth. For instance, Lin and Sosin (2001) analyzed African, Asian and Latin American data to find that debt has a negative and significant relationship with economic growth in the case of African countries, whereas for Latin American and Asian the relationship of debt and economic growth is positive but statistically insignificant. Moreover, Lin and Sosin (2001) concluded that debt only promotes economic growth when it is reasonably allocated. Pattillo et al. (2002) proved that the effect on growth of debt could be positive at a low level of debt, but negative at higher levels of debt over GDP.

Opposing the previous views, other studies have found out a negative relationship between debt and growth. In order to measure debt overhang Deshpande (1997) compared the growth rate of 13 severely indebted countries, unveiling that debt burden has a negative effect on labour and capital productivity, thereby adversely affecting economic growth. Similarly, Cunningham (1993) using pooled, cross sectional and time series for 16 Heavily Indebted Countries over 1971-1979 and 1980-1987 discovered a strong negative relationship between economic growth and debt burden for the 1971-1979 period. Afxentiou and Serletis (1996a) analyzed

55 developing countries during the period 1970-1990 finding out that in the 1970-1980 period external debt did not affect growth negatively, in 1980-1990 the relationship was negative and for 1970-1990 period, a reduced importance of debt overhang was observed. Sawada (1994) has found a similar negative effect of the debt burden for 22 highly indebted countries during the period 1955-1990 concluding that highly indebted countries share a debt overhang problem.

Recently, Siddiqui and Malik (2010) used panel series to analyse the case of Pakistan during the period 1972-2010, showing that external debt is negatively associated with economic growth. Moreover, they suggested that an increase in external debt leads to a decline in economic growth. Elwasila Mohammed (2011) has also proved a similar negative effect of the debt burden for the case of Sudan over the period 1969-2009.

This sometimes perceived negative relationship between debt and growth is often related to a mismanagement of financial resources. Evidence from Ajayi (2002) supports an association between debt and some internal factors of debtor countries. Ajayi (2002) analyzed 14 West African countries using data from 1970 to 2008 to discover that the negative effects of external debt on growth have a great correlation with economic policy errors such as mismanagement, high budget deficit, wrong exchange rate policies and corruption. Another example can be found in Burger and Warnock (2006), who having used panel data from the Bank of International Settlements for 49 emerging and advanced countries, found that improving policy performance and strengthening institutions may favour economic

growth among debtor countries. Recently, Kim et al. (2015) used data of 77 countries from 1990 to 2014 to reveal that an interaction term between public debt and corruption is statistically significant. Problems such as corruption or the malfunctioning of institutions (rule of law, government accountability) are linked to the authoritarian or illiberal nature of many of these economies, a phenomenon that hinders their prospects of economic growth (Ponomariov et al. 2017; Budina et al. 2023; Gigineishvili et al. 2023).

In spite of the increasing importance of external debt flows, the relationship between debt and growth amongst Central Asian countries has not been adequately studied so far. The Central Asian countries case is the best example for the interpretation of the so-called South-South cooperation, as former Soviet Republics can enjoy from Chinese loans. Therefore, in this paper we analyse the main features of the debt flows recently received by Central Asian countries, in order not only to infer conclusions about the nature of Central Asian countries debt, but also to suggest policy recommendations for governments to improve debt management. It is too soon to examine whether the South-South Cooperation (mainly from China) will be more effective for economic growth; however, it is still essential to assess the role recently played by loans mainly from OECD countries.

The main objective of this research is to analyse external debt effects on growth using a time series methodology (employing annual data from 2000 to 2017 for the Central Asian countries' economy). Our hypotheses are tested utilizing the random-

effect, fixed-effects, OLS, and dynamic panel data regression models. Furthermore, to avoid spurious regression results, data are tested for the presence of unit roots using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test (Dickey and Fuller, 1979) and Phillips-Perron Test (Phillips and Perron, 1988).

We attempt to assess the effect of external debt on economic growth among Central Asian countries with the purpose of testing the following hypotheses:

H1: The growth of a nation's debt amount has a negative effect on economic growth mainly in those countries whose institutions' quality is low.

H2: External debt is more likely associated with a lower standard of living (lower per capita GDP) among those Central Asian countries less integrated in the world trade system.

The remainder of the article will be as follows: after the brief introduction Section 2 discusses a literature review on the topic of study, whereas Section 3 describes the basic features of debt amongst Central Asian countries. Section 4 presents the specification of the applied model. Section 5 presents the empirical results regarding the effect of external debt on per capita GDP levels amongst Central Asian countries. The final section concludes the paper and suggests some policy implications.

2. Literature review

Debt effect on growth is amongst the earliest and most enticing discussions in economics. Numerous studies have been carried out on the relationship between debt and economic growth over the last three decades.

Regarding the New- Keynesian approach on debt overhang and institutions' role, Krugman (1988) argued in the late 1980s that debt overhang occurs when the present value of the expected income of a country is less than the accumulated debt. Moreover, Keynesian models focus on the role of government in the economic growth process, suggesting that in case there is a gap between savings and investment, then this deficit can be filled by public debt. However, according to Classical economists, government intervention should be limited so as to allow the economy behave freely, warning about excessive debt accumulation over the time. Crowding out effects are mentioned among others to warn against high external indebtedness.

Among debt supporters, Cline (1995) argued that there is a positive relationship between debt and economic growth of the borrowing country only when debt's marginal productivity is greater the interest payment. Amoateng and Amoako (1996), using panel data for 35 African countries over the period 1960 – 1990, found that there is a unidirectional and positive causal relationship between debt services and economic growth. Akram (2001) found that current debt flows stimulate investment whereas past debt accumulation discourages investment. Supported by the above findings, Joyaraman and Lau (2009) used panel data of six Pacific islands

over the period 1988-2004 finding that one percentage increase of external debt stock leads to a 0.25 percent increase in national output. However, the Granger causality relationship between real domestic growth and external debt is only significant in the short-run, whereas it remains insignificant in the long run.

According to some studies, external debt contributes positively to growth only up to a certain point, after which its contribution becomes negative (Soldatova, 2006). Blavy (2006) estimated the 'threshold level of debt' in 21% of GDP: below that level debt is positively associated with productivity, but above the threshold debt level the coefficient becomes negative and significant. However, the hypothesis regarding the existence of a debt-threshold effect on growth was not been supported by Chudik et al. (2017).

Other studies defend that external debt reduces growth. Cunningham (1993) using time series data for the period 1977 to 2012 found out that debt burden has a negative effect on economic growth because of the impact on the productivity of labour and capital.

Afxentiou (1993) used the ARDL, co-integration and Granger causality test to examine the relationship between debt and GNP growth amongst 20 middle-income developing countries covering the period 1971-1988, finding a negative impact of foreign indebtedness on growth. Furthermore, Afxentiou suggested that development will occur in debtor country only in case external debt is converted into capital formation and other necessary inputs. Confirming the Afxentiou's conclusion, later Karagol (2002) used the same test used by Afxentiou and examined

the case of Turkey during the period 1956-1996. Karqagol found a negative correlation between external debt and economic growth. It should also be noted that the co-integration and Granger causality tests had also been used by Singh (1999) when investigating the case of India during the period 1980-2012.

Iyoha (1999), analyzing the case of Sub Saharian African countries over the period 1984-1997, asserted that mounting external debt depresses investment through both a “disincentive” effect and a “crowding out” effect and showed that 20% debt stock reduction would have increased investment by 18% and increased gross domestic product by 1%. Later Clements et al. (2003) after examining 55 low-income countries from 1970 to 1999 found that a substantial reduction of external debt for highly indebted poor countries¹ would increase per capita income growth by about one percentage point a year. In the same vein, Clements et al. (2003) on their investigation have proved Deshpande (1997) conclusion on the negative relationship between external debt and investment.

Following a similar procedure, Hassan and Akhtar (2012) analysed the case of Bangladesh over the period 1959-1995 to find a negative impact of both domestic and external debts on economic growth. Umaru et al. (2013) using panel data in the case of Nigeria over the period 1970-2010 discovered that external debt has exerted a negative impact on economic growth opposed to domestic debt, which impacted positively on economic growth.

¹ According to Birdsall et al., (2002) highly indebted poor countries have 3 main common characteristics: (a) they incurred heavy debt mainly in the 1970s but the symptoms of highly indebted poor countries emerged in 1980s; (b) debt ratio of these countries is much higher than other low income or developing countries; and (c) they are poor countries with a lower economic growth.

Recently, Siddique and Selvanathan (2015) have based their analysis on panel data for 40 highly indebted poor countries over the period 1970-2007, in order to reveal that in the short-run as well as in the long-run, a reduction in debt stock would have significantly increased the growth performance of indebted nations.

As a result of utilizing a multiple step regression for a country data panel, De Soyres et al. (2022) found that an unexpected rise in public debt to GDP reduces the GDP level in countries either with a previous high debt record or with a prior rising debt trajectory.

Additionally, a part of the literature has underlined the importance of good policies and institutions in maximizing the effectiveness of debt: Savvides (1992), who asserted that debt payments might negatively affect the country's economic performance when a debtor country is unable to pay its external debt, underlined the issue of governance.

Afxentiou et al. (1996a) affirmed that debt discourages economic growth if borrowing countries misallocate received external debt. Arslanalp and Henry (2004) claimed that the problem faced by highly indebted countries is the lack of effective institutions. Aminu et al. (2013: 9-11) mentioned, "if a government has a high discount factor, it will rather consume than invest once debt relief is granted". Kraay and Nehru (2006) applied a dynamic panel probit specification in order to prove that debt distress relies not only on the level of debt over GDP, but also on each country's economic policies and institutions.

Additionally, Mohammed (2018) empirically investigated the case of Sudan over the period 1969-2015 discovering that there is a great correlation between institutions' quality and debt reduction. He suggests that the government should ensure macroeconomic and price stability so as to maintain access to foreign loans to supplement the low levels of domestic savings. Zanna et al. (2019) have revealed that the success of debt-financed investment among developing countries depends critically on the small details of public contracts.

From the above-listed review of empirical studies, it is quite clear that debt may not always be successful in promoting economic growth. It seems that past external debt has contributed to growth whilst future debt accumulation adversely affects economic growth. From this literature review, we should learn that debt should be channelled to favour economic growth and social sectors in order to optimize its impact on economic growth. It seems clear that in case the external debt is reasonably managed by the debtor country, the accumulation of external debt will not cause a reduction in economic growth.

3. Patterns of debt burden in Central Asian countries

Central Asian countries have achieved relative political stability as macroeconomic indicators of the country have improved since the Tajik civil war (1992-1997), the Tulip Revolution (2005) and regime changes (2010, 2020)

Kyrgyzstan, and the Islamic Movement of Uzbekistan insurgency in Uzbekistan (IMU, 1991-2001).

However, the levels of external debt and the size of the shadow economy are a continuous and serious concern. Despite the poor level of institutional quality in Central Asian countries, donor countries and international institutions provide financial resources to Central Asian countries.

Sarkisants (1999) asserts that the danger of extreme borrowing negatively affected the economy when the threshold level of debt is above 50% of GDP, while Blavy (2006) argued the negative effect of debt overhang with 21% to GDP. Nevertheless, the Central Asian countries paid very little attention in the past to the problem of the overhang external debt and ways to resolve it.

If the total external debt index for 2000, using the chaining method, is taken as 100% throughout all 17 years, external debt in all Central Asian countries exceeded its maximum value from 1.7 to 11.7 times. For instance, the external debt of Kazakhstan increased 11.7 times or by 1173.9% in 2017 compared to 2000. Following, Kyrgyzstan 352.3%, Uzbekistan 326.4%, and Turkmenistan 32.3%, respectively. Worthy to note that the total external debt of Tajikistan has decreased 62.9% in recent one and half decades (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. External Debt (% GDP) and GDP Growth Rate

Source: World Development Indicators, 2020; International Monetary Fund, 2020.

Although generally exhibiting a rising trend, figure1 shows us that the growth rate for Central Asian countries was averaged 6.5%, and the lower average growth between 2000 and 2017 was associated with much higher external debt to GDP

ratios. The growth rate decreased during 2007-2009 due to global financial and economic crisis and 2014-2017 due to the ongoing financial crisis started from 2015 among the Commonwealth Independent States.

The average growth rate decreased from 8.9% to 4.1% (-53.9) from 2007 to 2017 in the case of Kazakhstan's economy. Meanwhile, the total external debt of Kazakhstan has increased from 90.7 in 2007 to 127.1% in 2015 and it has steadily decreased to 17.6% in 2017. Meanwhile, because of the government's more liberal economic policy, a rise in government bond yields has taken place (from 10% to 16% in reference to short-term bonds). However, there has not been a clear worsening of government accounts, since deficit and debt over GDP still reveal rather low values, 1% and 23% respectively for 2023 (World Bank, 2024b).

In the last ten years, the average growth rate in Kyrgyzstan has decreased from 8.5 to 4.7%, however total external debt increased to 31.1% from 2007 to 2015 while steadily decreasing to 22.7% in 2017. The growth rate of Tajikistan² remained in its position to 7.9-7.3% in the recent ten years, although an external debt of the country reaches 40.3% in 2017.

For ten of the seventeen years under review, the growth rate in Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan has decreased by 52.9 and 57.8%, while the external debt of both countries has increased 1.8 times or 181.6% and 9,3 times or 930.3%, respectively.

Uzbekistan has recently undergone relevant changes in its foreign policy, after the accession of Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the country's leadership. Mirziyoyev has

² Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Tajikistan. Public Debt Statement 2018 http://minfin.tj/downloads/otchet_2018vd.pdf

clearly opted for a liberal approach to neighbouring Central Asian Countries, for instance favouring trade flows or trying to solve the bilateral frontiers disputes. In spite of these efforts, the transition to a more liberalized trade policy focus in the region is far from being accomplished. However, Uzbekistan has managed to reduce both its budget deficit (2.4%) and debt (44%) over GDP, which still show a higher value in comparison with Kazakhstan figures (World Bank, 2024a).

Some experts point to the following reasons for the world financial and economic crisis of 2008-2010 caused a debt problem. According to Nobel Prize-Winners in Economics Ionnides and Pissarides (2015) the 2008-2010 crisis was unusual because everything started with the financial sector and then spilt over into debt problems. During the world financial and economic crisis in 2008-2010 Central Asian countries mostly suffered from the rising world hydrocarbon prices. For example, the price of 1,000 c. m. of natural gas imported into Tajikistan from 2007 to 2010 increased 2.8 times, i.e. from 100 USD in 2007 to 280 USD in 2010³. It should be noted that an increase in the price of energy resources was the next negative impact on the Central Asian economy during the financial and economic crisis. For example, in Uzbekistan, with its 8 million tons of gas condensate

³ See: Strategy of the Economic Development and Business Support Program for 2010-2011, Branch of the Open Society Institute-Assistance Fund in Tajikistan, Dushanbe, 2010.

annually,⁴; the price of energy resources had extremely increased to 32%, followed to Tajikistan 16%, and Kyrgyzstan 15%⁵.

Siwiniska (2000) analyzed seven Post-Soviet countries including two Central Asian countries discovering that the main cause of the rapid increase of external debt in Post-Soviet countries had a great relationship with the fiscal imbalance of these countries. This author also noted that the large share of fixed expenditures (interest payments, pension payments) in total expenditures, which makes it hard to lower their level, also worsens the fiscal imbalances. Helbling et al. (2004) used panel data for 7 Commonwealth of Independent State⁶ countries to suggest that the main cause of the rapid increase of external debt was due to output decline and the lack of multilateral grant finance, instead of loans. In addition, they concluded that fiscal and other reforms, and consequently, growth revival, took longer than expected.

4. Model Specification and Estimation Method

As discussed in the previous section, the main goal of this paper is to examine the relationship between external debt and per capita GDP growth in Central Asian countries.

⁴ <http://www.profi-forex.org>, 22 February, 2012.

⁵ See: Growth Returning to Emerging Europe and Central Asia, Press Release, WB, Washington, 2011, 433/ECA.

⁶ The Soviet Union with 15 republics ceased to exist in 1991, when the Commonwealth of Independent States was established.

Following the basic neoclassical growth model by Solow (1956) our specification can be written as follows:

$$Y_t = A_t K_t^a (H C_t L_t)^\beta \dots (1)$$

where Y is per capita gross domestic product (GDP) in real terms; L and K denote, respectively, labour (employment) and physical capital inputs, HC denote skilled labour migrant, A is a measure of technology and exogenous knowledge; alpha a is the share of capital; β is the share of labour (participation ratio), while t represents time.

We linearise (1), taking logs and differencing, obtaining the following expression that describes the determinants of the growth rate of real GDP :

$$L_- Y_t = a L_-(K_t) + \beta L_-(L_t) + L_-(H_t) + L_-(A_t) \dots (2)$$

While many empirical studies have traced the effect of debt on growth through investment and savings (Hoffman and Reisen, 1991; Andreas, 1992; Cohen, 1993; Agenor and Montiel 1996; and Fosu, 1999), a few have attempted to analyse debt's effect on growth taking into account the influence of institutions. Thus, taking into account the objective of researching the effect of external debt on economic growth we have additionally included one variable, which measures the level of corruption of each country. In addition to this, the control variables that conventionally appear in economic growth models such as openness to trade, foreign investment as a

percentage of GDP, labour force growth, government size and inflation are included as independent variables. Applying these changes to equation 2, the final model will be rewritten as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} L_GDPpc_t = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 L_ (EDSmm_t) + \beta_2 L_ (EDexp_t) + \beta_3 L_ (CPIAtac) \\ & + \beta_4 L_ (Govexp_t) + \beta_5 L_ (LF) + \beta_6 L_ (FDI_t) + \beta_7 L_ (INF_t) \\ & + \beta_8 L_ (OPN_t) + \varepsilon_t \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

As shown by the hypotheses put forward, we expect that β_1 and β_2 (external debt stocks as a % of GDP and external debt stocks as a % of exports of goods, services and primary income, our proxy for the debt burden) are more likely associated with a lower standard of living (lower per capita GDP) among recipient countries when applying the most appropriate institutional policies β_3 (level of institutions).

We have included β_4 (government size which is measured by government consumption ratio to GDP), β_5 (labour force growth) as control variables.

Following them we also included β_6 net inflow of foreign direct investment to GDP, β_7 inflation, while β_8 openness are to be controlled for. Munzara (2015: 87-88) asserts that economic growth tends to be related to the international trade patterns of a country because the opening of trade enlarges the size of the market so that domestic firms can grow through exporting to the rest of the world”.

According to Solow’s (1956) growth model, there are three sources of economic growth which are capital accumulation, labour force growth (β_5) and technological progress. Baumol and Blinder (2009) contend, “for a given technology

and a given labour force, labour productivity will be higher when capital stock is larger”.

It is worthwhile to mention that the positive association between technology and economic growth makes possible for debtor countries to access intermediate inputs and advanced technologies, leading to higher productivity of labour. The β coefficients of the explanatory variables, reflect the elasticity of the real GDP with respect to each of these variables and ε is a disturbance term, which is assumed to be normally distributed.

5. Results and Discussion

To determine the order of integration, we used three-unit root tests, the Augmented-Dickey Fuller test (comparing AIC and BIC criterion), DF-GLS test comparing modified AIC and BIC criterion using Perron-Qu method and first differences. Results are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1 shows all variables were confirmed to be stationary except L_INF which is not stationary in any order. The L_GDPpc, L_EDexp, and L_CPIAtac became stationary after first difference at 5% and 10%, respectively. The remaining variables L_EDS, L_OPN, and L_POP are stationary in both orders. The L_GovEx and L_FDI became stationary at the first difference.

Table 1. Summary of ADF and DF-GLS unit root tests

	ADF Test			DF-GLS Test (Perron -Qu)		Overall conclusion
		Test	Conclusion	Test	Conclusion	
L_GDPpc_t	τ_t	-1.08811	Stationary	0.0918129	Nonstationary	Stationary
ΔL_GDPpc_t	τ_μ	0.218050**	Stationary	-0.197132***	Stationary	
L_EDS_t	τ_t	-1.14090***	Stationary	-0.01571***	Stationary	Stationary
ΔEDS_t	τ_μ	0.498619***	Stationary	-0.0721988	Nonstationary	
L_EDEX_t	τ_t	-0.519867	Nonstationary	0.0232166	Nonstationary	Stationary
$\Delta EDEX_t$	τ_μ	-0.649048*	Stationary	0.04052*	Stationary	
$L_CPIAtac_t$	τ_t	-1.25182	Nonstationary	0.00177465	Nonstationary	Stationary
$\Delta CPIAtac_t$	τ_μ	0.519129**	Stationary	0.01929*	Stationary	
L_GovExp_t	τ_t	-1.46868***	Stationary	-0.00200849	Nonstationary	Nonstationary
$\Delta GovExp_t$	τ_μ	0.148321	Nonstationary	-0.0216979	Nonstationary	
L_OPN_t	τ_t	-1.06519***	Stationary	-0.005128***	Stationary	Stationary
ΔL_OPN_t	τ_μ	0.495176***	Stationary	-0.05858	Nonstationary	
L_POP_t	τ_t	-1.47189***	Stationary	0.003423	Nonstationary	Stationary
ΔL_POP_t	τ_μ	0.429150***	Stationary	0.0814704	Nonstationary	
L_FDI_t	τ_t	-0.928274***	Stationary	0.0452527*	Stationary	Stationary
ΔL_FDI_t	τ_μ	-0.132794	Nonstationary	0.442711	Nonstationary	
L_INF_t	τ_t	-0.222798	Nonstationary	0.101096	Nonstationary	Nonstationary
ΔL_INF_t	τ_μ	-0.594451	Nonstationary	-0.0205564	Nonstationary	

Source: Authors' computation.

Note: the lag of ADF test is determined by the AIC and BIC values.

Lag order is shown in parenthesis based on AIC and BIC at ADF level.

*, ** and *** indicate significant at 1%, 5% and 10%, respectively.

τ_t - Means trend and intercept; τ_μ - Means intercept.

We found similar results on the DF-GLS Test where L_GDPpc , L_EDexp , and $L_CPIAtac$ became stationary after first differencing at 1% and 10%, respectively. The L_OPN and L_FDI again become stationary after first differencing, whereas L_EDS , L_GovEx , L_POP , and L_INF are not stationary in both orders.

Table 2 shows the results of all models' regressions. As shown in Table 2, the regression coefficient of L_EDS (external debt stock % over GDP) and L_EDEX (external debt stocks as a percentage of exports of goods, services and primary income) have a negative effect on Central Asian economy and highly significant which ranges from -0.21^{***} to -0.59^{***} .

However, it is worthwhile to mention that the negative effect of external debt is also often associated with the poor level of the institutions and governance, i.e. with the level of corruption and misuse of foreign debt in Central Asian countries.

Moreover, the negative result might be having a direct relationship with debt overhang effect or Ricardian effect, which means that a current high external debt stock would suggest that there would be taxes on future income in order to make debt repayments, and in consequence there could be a reduction in economic growth.

Table 2 shows the coefficients of government expenditure ranges from -0.57^{**} to -0.68^{**} and level of corruption also suggesting its significant negative coefficients that ranges from -1.14^{**} to -1.29^{***} . However, the regression results of the Models 5 and 7 reveal a positive but not statistically significant sign.

Furthermore, openness, labour force and foreign direct investment are all found to have a significant positive impact on economic growth. The coefficient associated with openness is positive and statistically significant at 1% and 5% level of significance in the Models 2 and 4. Experts argue that opening to trade enlarges the size of the market so that domestic firms can grow through exporting to the rest of the world.

Labour force growth is statistically significant at 1% and 5% level in Models 2,3, and 4. According to Munzara (2015: 88) “a higher population growth rate leads to a higher steady-state economic growth rate because, in the long-run equilibrium, all aggregate variables (production, capital, and labour) increase at the rate of population growth.”

In addition, the coefficient for the FDI variable is also statistically significant at 1%, 5% and 10% in Models 1, 6, and 7, respectively.

The results confirm the finding of Savvides (1992), Afxentiou et al., (1996a), Lin and Sosin (2001), Ajayi (2002) Arslanalp and Henry (2004), and Buffe and Atolia (2012) suggesting that external debt effectiveness depends on institutional quality of the recipient country. Moreover, our results confirm the finding of Sawada (1994), Fosu (1996), Pattillo et al. (2002), who argue on the negative effect of debt overhang on economic growth through reductions in investment levels.

Table 2. Impact of Foreign Debt on Economic Growth in Central Asian countries.

Dependent variable GDPpc.

Variables	Model 1 (OLS)	Model 2 (FE)	Model 3 (FE)	Model 4 (RE)	Model 5 (RE)	Model 6 (WLS)	Model 7 (DP-1)
L_EDS	-0.723779 (0.0088***)	-0.164531 (0.0679**)	-0.257515 (0.3882*)	-0.213043 (0.0007***)	0.00746 (0.9790)	0.7677130 (0.0051***)	0.310581 (0.2067)
L_EDEX	-0.595276 (0.0096***)	-0.596022 (0.0356**)	-0.315562 (0.1825*)	-0.324353 (0.1121)	-0.631837 (0.0052**)	-0.683222 (0.0003***)	-0.149378 (0.4538)
L_CPIAtac	-1.29149 (0.0049***)	0.075162 (0.7498)	-1.16608 (0.0157**)	0.0470215 (0.8145)	-1.14083 (0.0385**)	-1.55431 (0.0036**)	-1.22106 (0.0415**)
L_GovExp	-0.443026 (0.1968)	-0.575275 (0.0124**)	-0.138208 (0.6817*)	-0.683463 (0.0031***)	-0.82680 (0.3709)	-0.602100 (0.0763*)	-0.457432 (0.1899)
L_OPN	0.584759 (0.2657)	0.425237 (0.0992*)	0.376352 (0.4465)	0.641077 (0.0064***)		0.322652 (0.4899)	-0.024134 0 (0.9781)
L_POP	0.356522 (0.3547)	0.265721 (0.0601*)	0.539968 (0.0280**)	0.284306 (0.0370**)		0.300033 (0.1798)	0.0172830 (0.9664)
L_FDI	0.0657432 (0.4461*)	0.0929577 (0.2755)			0.112301 (0.1833)	0.151894 (0.0004***)	0.0708032 (0.0479**)
L_INF	-0.129200 (0.2423)	-0.239522 (0.1606)	-1.45065 (0.0394**)		0.02175 (0.8860)	-0.123092 (0.2624)	-0.073180 0 (0.7065)
Constant	-4.57658 (0.6045)	-2.59820 (0.4172)	-1.05563 (0.8861**)	-5.04805 (0.0932*)	5.39480 (0.1310)	-1.42105 (0.8155)	-0.09149 (0.0064**)
R-squared	0.511329					0.810561	
Adjusted R	0.423619					0.768463	
Mean dep. var	1.546141	1.609350	1.546141	1.609350	1.550761	1.550761	
Log-likelihood	-22.64774	-44.38080	-15.34953	-55.50382	-23.14750	-61.76302	
Schwarz criterion	76.09666	137.2355	80.75098	133.0412	88.16828	157.7860	
Akaike criterion	61.29547	110.7616	56.69906	121.0076	68.29499	141.5260	
Hannan-Quinn	66.86526	121.3905	65.74996	125.8389	75.70356	147.5876	
Durbin-Watson	1.927806	1.917564	1.876106	1.876944	1.754686		
Test for AR(1) errors							z = -2.12287 (0.0338)
Test for AR(2) errors							z = 1.45085 (0.1468)
Chi-square							14.6192 (0.6229)

Source: Authors' computation.

* , ** and *** indicate significant at 1%, 5% and 10%, respectively.

Table 3. Correlation coefficients, using the observations 2000–2017

	L_GDPpc	L_EDS	L_EDEX	L_CPIAcor	L_GovExp	L_OPN	L_POP	L_FDI	L_INF
L_GDPpc	1.000								
L_EDS	-0.093	1.000							
L_EDEX	-0.046	0.164	1.000						
L_CPIAtac	-0.346	0.034	0.1645	1.000					
L_GovExp	-0.006	0.051	0.0344	0.0698	1.000				
L_OPN	-0.458	0.198	0.0514	-0.5528	-0.3244	1.000			
L_POP	0.155	-0.549	0.1982	-0.3561	0.2435	-0.479	1.000		
L_FDI	0.045	-0.672	-0.5490	-0.4358	0.3660	0.4266	-0.557	1.000	
L_INF	-0.091	0.164	-0.6720	0.2456	0.0726	0.4161	0.405	-0.094	1.000

**Table 4. Summary Statistics, using the observations 2000–2017
(after the log transformation)**

Variable	Mean	Median	S.D.	Min	Max
L_GDPpc	1.61	1.62	0.531	0.453	2.62
L_EDS	3.66	4.04	1.27	0.037	5.01
L_EDEX	5.18	5.15	0.385	4.17	5.88
L_CPIAtac	0.85	0.91	0.335	0.095	1.44
L_GovExp	2.54	2.59	0.311	1.78	3.00
L_OPN	4.49	4.54	0.407	3.39	5.17
L_POP	16.1	15.8	0.676	15.3	17.3
L_FDI	1.30	1.49	1.091	-2.51	3.11
L_INF	2.00	1.93	0.683	-0.945	3.65

Table 5. Variables, measures and data sources.

Variable	Measurement	Data source
L_GDPpc	Natural logarithm of GDP per capita	World Development Indicators (http://databank.worldbank.org)
L_EDS	External debt stocks (% of GDP)	World Development Indicator (http://databank.worldbank.org)
L_EDEX	External debt stocks (% of exports of goods, services and primary income)	World Development Indicator (http://databank.worldbank.org)
L_CPIAtac	Transparency, accountability, and corruption in the public sector rating (1=low to 6=high)	World Bank's Country Policy and Institutional Assessment
L_OPN	Ratio of the sum of imports and exports to the GDP that provides the measure of openness of economy	World Development Indicator (http://databank.worldbank.org)
L_GovExp	General government final consumption expenditure (% of GDP)	World Development Indicator (http://databank.worldbank.org)
L_FDI	FDI, net inflows (% of GDP)	World Development Indicator (http://databank.worldbank.org)
L_POP	Labour force participation rate	World Development Indicator (http://databank.worldbank.org)
L_INF	Logarithm of (1 + inflation rate)	World Development Indicator (http://databank.worldbank.org)

6. Conclusions

This paper examined the effect of external debt on the economic growth in Central Asian countries over the period 2000-2017. Results indicate that external debt has a negative effect on the economic growth among Central Asian countries.

After the collapse of the USSR, the post-Soviet Union's Central Asian countries took urgent measures to minimize the negative consequences of the collapse of the economy. It took a decade for the former post-Soviet Union's Central Asian countries to become integrated into the world economy in order to attract external financial inflows. Nevertheless, their efforts remain relatively ineffective mainly due to the poor level of institutional quality, as showed by our analysis results, what seems to confirm the first hypothesis put forward. Additionally, our

second hypothesis appears to be confirmed only in two of our models. For the other ones the effect of openness on growth is not statistically significant.

Another reason for the negative association between external debt and economic growth is the threshold level of debt is above 21% of GDP (Sarkisants, 1999) or 35-40% of GDP (Maria Levina, 2019) among Central Asian countries. Debt overhang indicates a high marginal tax rate on future output on the country, leading to a slowdown in investment rate growth thus reducing output growth directly by sinking productivity.

The vast array of literature argues that external debt could provoke an economic slowdown when external debt is not rationally utilized and optimally managed. Therefore, given the challenges faced by the Central Asian economies, the Central Asian governments need to be made responsible for the accountability of external debt use. Those accountability levels must be enforced so that external debt is channelled to favour economic growth and social sectors, with the purpose of reorienting external debt in order to optimize its impact on economic growth and poverty reduction in each country.

References

- Abbas, S.M. (2005). Public debt sustainability and growth in post-HIPC Sub-Saharan Africa: the role of DD. Paper for GD Net's 2004/05 Project on Macroeconomic Policy Challenges of Low Income Countries.
- Afxentiou, Panos C. and Serletis, Apostolos (1996a): "Foreign Indebtedness in Low and Middle Income Developing Countries", *Social and Economic Studies*, Cilt 45, Sayı 1, pp 133-159.
- Agenor, Pierre-Richard, and Peter Montiel (1996). *Development Macroeconomics* (Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press).
- Ajayi, S.I. (2003). *External debt, capital flight, and growth in Nigeria*". Trento, N.J.: Africa: World Press.
- Aminu, Umaru and Ahmad Aminu, Hamidu and Salihu, Musa (2013), *External Debt and Domestic Debt impact on the growth of the Nigerian Economy*. MPRA Paper No. 75122, Available at: <https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/75122/>
- Amoateng, K. and A.B. Amoaku, (1996). Economic Growth, export and external debt causality: The case of African countries. *Appl. Econ.*, 28: 21-27.
- Amos Tendai Munzara (2015). *Impact of Foreign Debt on Economic Growth in Zimbabwe*. *IOSR Journal of Economic and Finance*. Volume 6. Issue 5. Ver. II. Pp. 87-91.

- Arslanalp, S. and P.B. Henry, (2004). Helping the Poor to Help Themselves: Debt Relief or Aid?, Working Paper 10234, National Bureau of Economic Research, Cambridge, MA.
- Audu, I. (2004). The Impact of External Debt on Economic Growth and Public Investment: The Case of Nigeria, African Institute for Economic Development and Planning (IDEP), Dakar.
- Baumol, W.J., and Blinder, A. S. (2009). Macroeconomics: Principles and Policy (11th edition). USA: South- Western Cengage Learning.
- Birdsall, N., Williamson, J., and Deese, B. (2002). Delivering on Debt Relief: From IMF Gold to a New Aid Architecture. Co-published by the Center for Global Development and the Institute for International Economics, Washington.
- Budina, M. N., Ebeke, C., Ebeke, M. C. H., Jaumotte, M. F., Medici, A., Panton, A. J. & Yao, B. (2023). Structural Reforms to Accelerate Growth, Ease Policy Trade-Offs, and Support the Green Transition in Emerging Market and Developing Economies. *IMF Staff Discussion Note*, International Monetary Fund, Washington, DC.
- Burger, John D. and Francis E. Warnock. (2006). Local Currency and Bond Markets. IMF Staff papers, vol. 53, International Monetary Fund, Washington, D.C., pp 133-146.
- Burnside, C., and D. Dollar (2000). Aid, policies, and growth. *American Economic Review*, vol. 90, No. 4, pp. 847-868.

- Chudik, A., Mohaddes, K., Pesaran, M. H., & Raissi, M. (2017). Is There a Debt Threshold Effect on Output Growth? *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 99(1), pp 135-150.
- Clements, B., Bhattacharya, R., & Nguyen, T.Q. (2003). External Debt, Public Investment, and Growth in Low-Income Countries, IMF Working Paper WP/03/249, International Monetary Fund, Washington D.C.
- Cline, W. R. (1995). *International Debt Re-examined*. Washington DC: Peterson Institute for International Economics.
- Cohen, Daniel, (1993). Low Investment and Large LDC Debt in the 1980s,” *American Economic Review*, Vol. 83, No. 3 (June), pp. 437–49.
- Cunningham, R. T. (1993). The Effects of Debt Burden on Economic Growth in Heavily Indebted Nations. *Journal of Economic Development*, pp 115–126.
- De Soyres, C., Kawai, R., and Wang, M. (2022). Public Debt and Real GDP: Revisiting the Impact. *IMF Working Paper* WP/22/76, Washington DC: International Monetary Fund.
- Deshpande, A. (1997) The Debt Overhang and the Disincentive to Invest. *Journal of Development Economics*, pp 169–187.
- Dickey, D. A., and W. A. Fuller. (1979). Distribution of the estimators for autoregressive time series with a unit root. *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 74, no. 366a: 427-443. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01621459.1979.10482531>

- Easterly, W. (2003). The political economy of growth without development: A case study of Pakistan. In Dani Rodrik (Ed.), *Analytic Narratives on Economic Growth*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Elwasila S.E. Mohammed, (2011). Sustainability of Growth with a Non-renewable Resource and an External Debt Constraint: The Case of Sudan. Unpublished PhD Thesis, Graduate College, University of Khartoum.
- Eunji Kim, Yoonhee Ha, and Sangheon Kimv (2015). Public Debt, Corruption and Sustainable Economic Growth. *MDPI journal*, 9-43. doi:10.3390/su9030433
Available at: <https://www.mdpi.com/journal/sustainability>.
- Fosu, Augustin K., (1999). The External Debt Burden and Economic Growth in the 1980s: Evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa,” *Canadian Journal of Development Studies*, Vol. XX, No. 2, pp. 307–18.
- Gigineishvili, M. N., Teodoru, I. R., Karapetyan, N., Ustyugova, M. Y., van Houtte, M. J., Jonas, J., ... & Brollo, F. (2023). Paving the Way to More Resilient, Inclusive, and Greener Economies in the Caucasus and Central Asia. *IMF Departmental Paper 23/004*, International Monetary Fund, Washington, DC.
- Hasanov M., (2010). The World Financial and Economic and its Impact on Tajikistan,” *Central Asia and the Caucasus*, Volume 11, Issue 2. pp.13.29.
- Helbling, Thomas; Ashoka Mody, and Ratna Sahay, (2004). Debt Accumulation in the CIS-7 Countries: Bad Luck, Bad Policies, or Bad Advice? *IMF Working Paper*, Washington, D.C., 04/93: 3-40.

- Hoffman, B. and Reisen, H. (1991). Some Evidence on Debt-Related Determinants on Investment and Consumption in Heavily Indebted Countries. *Welt Wirtschaftliches Archive* 127(2): 280-297.
- Ionnides, Yannis and Christopher Pissarides (2015). Is the Greek debt crisis one of supply or demand? *Brooking Papers on Economic Activity*, Brooking Institution Press, pp 349-383.
- Jayaraman, T.K. & Lau, Evan, (2009). "Does external debt lead to economic growth in Pacific island countries," *Journal of Policy Modeling*, Elsevier, vol. 31(2), pages 272-288.
- Karagol, Erdal (2002). "The Causality Analysis of External Debt Service and GNP: The Case of Turkey," *Central Bank Review, Research and Monetary Policy Department*, Central Bank of the Republic of Turkey, vol. 2(1), pages 39-64.
- Kraay, A., & Nehru, V. (2006). When is external debt sustainable?. *The World Bank Economic Review*, 20(3), 341-365.
- Krugman, P. R. (1988). Financing versus Forgiving a Debt overhang. *Journal of Development Economics*, 29, pp 253-268.
- Levina, Maria (17 March 2019). Can Central Asia countries pay their external debts? *The Times of Central Asia*. Retrieved from: <https://www.timesca.com/index.php/news/26-opinion-head/20949-can-central-asia-countries-pay-their-external-debts>

- Limam Ould Mohamed Mahmoud (2015). The Role of External Debt on Economic Growth: Evidence from Mauritania. *International Journal of Economics & Management Sciences*. 4:4. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4172/2162-6359.1000240>
- Lin, S., and K. Sosin (2001). Foreign debt and economic growth. *Economics of Transition*, vol. 9, No. 3, pp 635-655.
- Milton A. Iyoha (1999). External debt and economic growth in sub-African countries: An econometric study AERC Research PaAfrican Economic Research Consortium, Nairobi.
- Naeem Akram (2011). Impact of Public Debt on the Economic Growth of Pakistan. *Pakistan development review*. pp. 599–615. DOI: 10.30541/v50i4IIpp.599-615
- Pattillo, C., H. Poirson, and R. Ricci (2002). External debt and growth. Working Paper, No. 02/69. Washington, D.C.: International Monetary Fund.
- Phillips, P. C. B. and Perron, P. (1988). Testing for a Unit Root in Time Series Regression (PDF). *Biometrika*. 75 (2): 335–346. doi:10.1093/biomet/75.2.335.
- Ponomariov, B., Balabushko, O., & Kisunko, G. (2017). Tax administration practices and firms' perceptions of corruption: evidence from Europe and Central Asia. (June 27, 2017). *World Bank Policy Research Working Paper*, (8122).
- Sarkisiant A.G. (1999). *Sistema mezhdunarodnykh dolgov*, OOO DeKA, Moscow, 720 pp.

- Savvides, Andreas (1992). Investment Slowdown in Developing Countries during the 1980s: Debt Overhang or Foreign Capital Inflows,” in *Kyklos*, Vol. 45, No. 3, pp. 363–78.
- Sawada, Yasuyuki. (1994). Are the Heavily Indebted Countries Solvent? Tests of Inter Temporal Borrowing Constraints. *Journal of Development Economics*, Cilt 45, pp 325-337.
- Siddiqui, R. and A. Malik (2010). Debt and Economic Growth in South Asia. *The Pakistan Development Review* 40:4, pp 677–688.
- Siwinska, Joanna (1999). The External Public Debt of Baltic and Selected CIS Countries in Years 1992–1997. Center for Social and Economic Research 169, Warsaw.
- Soldatova, E. I. (2005). Воздействие внешней задолженности на социально-экономическое развитие государств [The impact of external debt on the socio-economic development of states]. Moscow: ИТ МГУС.
- Solow, R. (1956). A contribution to the theory of economic growth. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, The MIT Press 70, (1956): 65-94. Available at: <http://piketty.pse.ens.fr/files/Solow1956.pdf>
- Szabo, Z. (2013). The effect of sovereign debt on economic growth and economic development. State Audit Office of Hungary, *Public Finance Quarterly*, 58 (3), pp 251-270.

Takhmina Akhther and Hashibul Hasan (2012), Impact of Public Debt Burden on Economic Growth: Evidence from Bangladesh, SSRN Electronic Journal, DOI: 10.2139/ssrn.2152592.

Warner, A. M. (1992). Did the Debt Crisis Cause the Investment Crisis? *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 107(4), pp 1161-1186.

World Bank (2024a): *Shaping tomorrow: Reforms for lasting Prosperity. Kazakhstan economic update.* World Bank, Washington DC.

World Bank (2024b): *Macro Poverty Outlook. Europe and Central Asia.* World Bank, Washington DC.

Zanna, L. F., Buffie, E. F., Portillo, R., Berg, A., & Pattillo, C. (2019). Borrowing for growth: big pushes and debt sustainability in low-income countries. *The World Bank Economic Review*, 33(3), 661-689.

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Appendix 1.

Figure A1. Central Asian countries: variables charts after the log transformation, 1997–2017.

Appendix 2. Charts of influential observations after the log transformation, 1997–2017.

Note: Cross-validation criterion = 9.27087